

FEM Simulation of MEMS Accelerometer

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Abstract. Accelerometers are sensors used to measure the magnitude of acceleration. In our paper, we have discussed a comb MEMS acceleration sensor. These sensors have wide applications in automotive industry. In our work, we have dealt with the eventual use as an impact sensor in airbags. In the first section, we will briefly discuss the airbag system and the working principle of the comb MEMS accelerometer. Then, in the second part, we will simulate the mechanical properties of the proposed sensor using Finite Element Method (FEM).

INTRODUCTION

In technical practice, the term sensor means a device that converts an input variable into electrical output signals. The input variable is most often a physical or chemical variable. The automotive industry is one of the main industries using sensors. Currently, up to 150 sensors can be found in modern vehicles and further growth is expected in the future. In our paper, we will discuss the topic of MEMS impact sensor for airbag system. The impact sensor is usually located on the edge of the vehicle where it senses the acceleration. If the vehicle decelerates suddenly, this deceleration is evaluated as an impact and the airbag is activated.

Car safety is one of the key demands for cars. Car safety can be divided into Passive Safety and Active Safety. Active safety ensures safe operation while driving under ordinary conditions. Passive safety ensures the protection of the participants in the event of a vehicle crash. Airbag systems can be classified under passive safety. One of the most important criteria in passenger protection is the maximum deceleration acting on the passenger. We can influence this deceleration by changing the duration of the impact. Crumple zones and airbags serve this purpose in the vehicle. An airbag is a bag of air that inflates on impact and catches the passenger to reduce the deceleration applied to them. Airbags are part of the Supplemental Restraint System (SRS) in a car.

The SRS system control unit receives input for parameters such as vehicle speed, steering, vehicle acceleration or seat belt activation. Based on this data, the control unit decides whether to activate the airbags and transmits this to the central control unit, which switches off the car's engine and other systems. The SRS control unit is usually located in the center of the vehicle. Along with the control unit, there is also an accelerometer that senses the overall acceleration of the vehicle. This sensor serves as a failsafe and an additional source of information for crash evaluation. The exact algorithms used to evaluate whether an airbag should be deployed are proprietary and different for each manufacturer. In general, however, we can say that airbags should be activated from speeds above 12-24 km/h. They also need to be inflated within 25-50 milliseconds of impact. Other requirements for an SRS system include the backup power supply in the event of a malfunction, diagnostic circuits to check the system during operation and safety circuits to prevent unintentional airbag activation.

MEMS ACCELEROMETER

The acronym MEMS stands for micro-electro-mechanical systems. They are small devices tens of micrometers in size that combine both electronics and moving parts. MEMS are commonly fabricated as microstructures on a silicon base. These micro devices can be used as sensors and actuators in many applications. Advantages of MEMS include, for example, small size and weight. Due to the small size, the amount of material consumed to produce the sensor is

lower, and combined with bulk manufacturing, these sensors are cheaper. Another advantage is the ability to integrate the auxiliary electronics together with the sensor into one compact unit.

MEMS acceleration sensors can perform various acceleration detection roles in the vehicle. For example, detecting acceleration values in a frontal or side impact to trigger seat belt pretensioners, airbag and rollover protection bar in the vehicle. Further applications are in the active safety of the vehicle in ABS and ESP systems. Other possible applications of acceleration sensors are in chassis control, suspension (active suspension) and vehicle alarm systems. In the case of airbag system, accelerometers are used to sense the negative acceleration of the vehicle. The control unit analyses the magnitude of the acceleration and decides whether to deploy the airbags in the vehicle. This type of sensors can send continuous acceleration information.

MEMS accelerometers are designed for different measurement ranges depending on the application. These measurement ranges are between 1 g and 400 g ($1 \text{ g} \approx 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$). For impact sensors, a range of 100g to 400g is used. The MEMS sensor is mounted together with the evaluating electronics in a single module, similar to an integrated circuit. This module, mounted on a small PCB and with other circuit components, is placed in a plastic housing. This housing is closed and sealed by a welded plastic lid. The sensor, after calibration and testing, sends its signal of through cable to the central airbag control unit. This sensor also includes an autocalibration option. In this process, the electrostatic force deflects the sensor structure to simulate acceleration in the vehicle and the response of the measured signal is compared to the reference value.

As can be seen in Fig.1 The comb MEMS accelerometer consists of four main parts, the anchors, the flexible mounting, the seismic mass, and the fixed electrodes. The anchors are used to firmly connect the moving part of the sensor to the sensor base substrate. The seismic mass with comb electrodes is connected to the anchors by means of flexible mounts. These elements form the core of the sensor which responds to changes in acceleration. Fixed electrodes are placed on the substrate, one on each side of the moving electrode. In this way, there is a pair of capacitors at each comb. Due to the acceleration, elastic deformation of the mounts and displacement of the seismic mass occurs. The displacement of the seismic mass changes the position of the moving electrodes, and this leads to a difference in the capacitances of C_1 and C_2 .

FIGURE 1. Scheme explaining the working principle of a capacitive MEMS accelerometer.

If we neglect the edge effects near the electrode edges and there is no acceleration applied to the sensor, the magnitude of the capacitance C for a single electrode is:

$$C = C_1 = C_2 = \epsilon \frac{A}{d} \quad (1)$$

Where ϵ is the permittivity of air, A is the electrode area and d is the electrode distance. This state when there is no acceleration applied to the sensor is called the neutral point. We assume that a horizontal acceleration is applied to

the sensor from the left side. An inertial force acts on the moving mass to move the electrode to the right direction by x , so the capacitances C_1, C_2 change as follows:

$$C_1 = \varepsilon \frac{A}{d+x} = C - \Delta C \quad (2)$$

$$C_2 = \varepsilon \frac{A}{d-x} = C + \Delta C \quad (3)$$

Consequently, we can determine the difference in capacitance ΔC :

$$C_2 - C_1 = 2\Delta C = \varepsilon \frac{A}{d-x} - \varepsilon \frac{A}{d+x} = \varepsilon A \frac{2x}{d^2-x^2} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta C = \varepsilon A \frac{x}{d^2-x^2} C \quad (5)$$

To achieve measurable capacitances, the individual electrodes for C_1 and C_2 are connected in parallel. The smallest capacitance changes ΔC that we can measure in a MEMS accelerometer are about 20 attoF (10^{-18}). Without the parallel connection, the capacitance difference would be undetectable. The output electrical signal, which is linearly dependent on acceleration, is obtained by evaluating the capacitance difference. Assume that a rectangular signal with a frequency of 1MHz and with a voltage of amplitude V_0 is applied from the oscillator to the left solid-state electrodes of the sensor. Then we bring to the right electrodes an inverse signal with the same frequency and amplitude. The whole system can be imagined as a simple voltage divider whose output is passed through a voltage follower and a demodulator. To evaluate the acceleration, we need to measure the voltage on the seismic mass V_x :

$$(V_x + V_0)C_1 + (V_x - V_0)C_2 = 0 \quad (6)$$

Combining the previous formulas, we get the relation between V_x and the displacement x :

$$V_x = V_0 \frac{C_2 - C_1}{C_2 + C_1} \quad (7)$$

$$C_2 - C_1 = \varepsilon A \frac{2x}{d^2-x^2} \quad (8)$$

$$C_2 + C_1 = \varepsilon A \frac{2d}{d^2-x^2} \quad (9)$$

$$V_x = V_0 \frac{x}{d} \quad (10)$$

The voltage on the seismic mass V_x has the form of a rectangular signal with amplitude directly proportional to the displacement of the mass x . The measured signal needs to be amplified and noise filtered out. If no acceleration occurs, the voltage output is zero. At the end, the signal passes through a demodulator where it is transformed to a constant voltage value proportional to the seismic mass displacement.

MODELING AND FEM SIMULATION

Based on the general information about MEMS impact sensor, we performed several FEA simulations on a specific geometry design to test its suitability for use as an impact sensor. In Fig. 2 we can see the geometry of the simulated sensor with corresponding dimensions. The sensor contains 24 sensing electrodes and 8 calibration electrodes. The calibration electrodes are used for automatic calibration of the sensor and are not involved in the measurement of impact. For measuring the acceleration on impact, we are only interested in the sensing electrodes, which are used to measure the acceleration.

FIGURE 2. Geometry and dimensions of simulated MEMS accelerometer.

We have modelled only the moving part of the sensor. However, we considered the need for static electrodes in the design. Therefore, the design assumes static electrodes at a distance of 2 μm from the moving electrodes. As a material for the sensor, we have chosen Polysilicon which is a standard material for the MEMS accelerometers. The material properties necessary in the simulation are given in Tab.1:

TABLE 1. Material properties of polysilicon

Property	Value
Density	2330 kg/m ³
Young's modul	1.7 $\times 10^{11}$ Pa
Poisson's ratio	0.22

The simulation was performed in ansys mechanical. For FEA, the model must first be discretized (meshed) using FEA elements. In our case, we have used so-called shell elements. These elements allow the simplification of a 3-D problem into a 2-D problem. Such an approach is suitable for solids that have a characteristic shape in one plane and are only "extruded" into 3-D space. These elements work on the pinciple that we create a planar mesh on the solid and then the depth of the body (the third dimension) is defined as a constant parameter. This approach allows to save the number of elements and thus to speed up the computation while maintaining the accuracy of the calculation. In designing the mesh, we used a denser mesh for flexible attachments and electrodes (Fig. 3). The resulting mesh had 19251 nodes and 14945 elements.

For the case of static structural and transient analysis, it was possible to use a simplified half model (Fig. 5 and Fig. 7). For these analyses, we set a symmetry boundary condition on the symmetry axis. This allowed us to simplify the model but retain precision.

FIGURE 3. Mesh used for simulation of MEMS accelerometer.

Modal Analysis

We performed a modal analysis first. The aim of this analysis is to find out the natural frequencies of the sensor. Since there are large deformations at resonance, if we were to excite sensor in the sensing direction it could cause unwanted activation of the sensor. For this simulation we needed to use a full sensor model. The sensor was rigidly fixed by anchors. The obtained resonance frequencies are shown in Tab.2. The table also specifies the plane in which the deformation occurs. The orientation of the planes is the same as in Fig.3.

TABLE 2. Resonance frequencies from modal analysis

Natural frequency	Value
First – ZY plane	14103 Hz
Second – ZY plane	27050 Hz
Third – ZY plane	29017 Hz
Fourth – XY plane	38274 Hz
Fifth– ZY plane	77905 Hz
Sixth– ZY plane	90458 Hz

Figure 4 shows the first and fourth mode. The fourth natural frequency is of interest since deformation of the sensor occurs in the direction of the acceleration measurement. Let's assume that at the lowest speed of 12km/h, the car is subjected to a maximum deceleration measured by the impact sensors of 400g. Then we can calculate the impact time as:

$$t = \frac{v}{a} = \frac{12/3,6}{400 \cdot 9,81} = 0,85 \text{ ms} \quad (11)$$

We compare this time with half the period of oscillation at the lowest resonance frequency. Half the period represents the time it takes for the mass to move in one direction.

$$\frac{T}{2} = \frac{1}{2f} = \frac{1}{14103,2} = 0,04 \text{ ms} \quad (12)$$

By comparison, we can state that even the fastest excitations measured by the impact sensors are about 10 times slower than excitations that could put the sensor into resonance.

It is important to note that the output of the modal analysis are only the natural frequencies and the deformation shapes. Modal analysis does not provide us with the quantitative magnitude of the displacements at resonance. It is because of this that we can see in Fig. 4b the unrealistic penetration of the mounting and measuring electrodes.

FIGURE 4. a) First mode deformation and b) fourth mode deformation

Transient Analysis

The second simulation was a transient mechanical simulation. For this simulation, a half model was sufficient. The transient simulation is a time-dependent simulation which means that it was necessary to define the change of acceleration over time. The anchors were rigidly fixed. At the beginning, the sensor was at standstill and no acceleration was acting on it. At a time of 0.001 ms, we applied a constant acceleration of 400g to the sensor. This acceleration was applied to the sensor for 0.85 ms and then dropped again to 0g. The simulation itself lasted until a time of 2 ms and no more acceleration was applied to the sensor. The aim was to verify if the sensor has sufficient dynamics to detect even the largest accelerations under impact conditions. In Fig.5 we can see the maximum equivalent Von-Mises stress from deformation. To better visualize the shape of the deformation, the deformation was scaled to be bigger. However, this is only a visual zoom which does not affect the results.

FIGURE 5. Maximum von Misses stress (91x bigger deformation scale)

As can be seen in Fig. 5 the maximum mechanical stress reaches 7.13 MPa. The ultimate strength of polysilicon is 1.45 GPa. From this we can see that even with the largest expected deformations of the sensor we have big safety factor. We can therefore conclude that this sensor design is sufficiently robust for the required purpose. In the plot in Fig. 6 we can see the displacement of seismic mass over time. As we can see, the sensor was able to settle down in 85 ms to a single value. From this we can tell that the dynamics of the sensor is sufficient to capture even the fastest motion we expect when sensing an impact.

FIGURE 6. Total displacement of sensor in time

Steady-State Analysis

As we have shown in the transient analysis, the simulated sensor can react fast enough to respond to the motion that generates on impact. This allows us to neglect transient events and assume that the sensor had enough time to reach the resulting position and thus perform a static analysis. For the static structural analysis, we again only need the half model of the sensor and set the symmetry in the simulation parameters. Figure 7 shows the elastic deformation of the sensor under a static load of 400g. In Tab. 3 the resulting electrode displacements for each simulated acceleration are shown. Using equation (5), we calculated the respective capacitance changes ΔC as a sum for all sensing electrodes (connected in parallel). If we assume that the voltage amplitude V_0 from the oscillator is 3.3V, then we can calculate the voltage on the seismic mass using equation (10). All the calculated values are in Tab. 3. We can calculate the total area of the measuring electrodes A in equation (5) as:

$$A = N_s \cdot L_f \cdot t \quad (13)$$

where N_s represents the number of electrodes, L_f represents the length of the moving electrode and t represents the thickness of the sensor.

FIGURE 7. Total displacement of sensor under a static load of 400g. (180x bigger deformation scale)

TABLE 3. Simulated and calculated results from steady-state analysis

Acceleration [g]	Displacement [nm]	Capacitance change ΔC [femtoF]	Voltage V_x [mV]
20	3,55	0,06	5,86
40	7,10	0,11	11,71
60	10,65	0,17	17,57
80	14,20	0,23	23,43
100	17,75	0,28	29,28
120	21,30	0,34	35,14
140	24,85	0,40	40,99
160	28,40	0,45	46,85
180	31,94	0,51	52,71
200	35,49	0,57	58,56
220	39,04	0,62	64,42
240	42,59	0,68	70,28
260	46,14	0,74	76,13
280	49,69	0,79	81,99
300	53,24	0,85	87,85
320	56,79	0,91	93,70
340	60,34	0,96	99,56
360	63,89	1,02	105,42
380	67,44	1,08	111,27
400	70,99	1,13	117,13

In Fig. 8 we can see the displacement of seismic mass relative to the acceleration. In the simulation, we considered linear elastostatic analysis. We could use this simplification because even at the highest accelerations the magnitudes of the seismic mass displacements are small (tens of nanometers) in comparison to geometry size (tens of

micrometers). The capacitance change is in the order of femtofarads, which is a measurable value, but it is still a very small capacitance. The voltage on the seismic mass varies from 5 to 117 millivolts. This voltage is sufficient to be further amplified and processed by the sensor's electronics. As a result, we can say that the analyzed MEMS accelerometer has fulfilled the requirements to be used as an impact sensor.

FIGURE 8. Relationship of the displacement of the seismic mass to the acceleration magnitude

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have discussed the topic of a comb MEMS accelerometer and its use as an impact sensor in an airbag system. First, we described the working principle of the MEMS accelerometer. Then, for a specific geometry, we performed several FEM simulations to investigate the possibility of using it as an impact sensor. From the simulation results we can say that the sensor fulfills the basic requirements. However, in the future it would be useful to perform further simulations dealing with other than purely mechanical aspects of the sensor.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by HORIZON EU "FreeTwinEV" project no. 101159989, and by Grant Agency KEGA, grant No. 006STU-4/2023.

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